

RESEARCH ARTICLE

An Assessment of Effective Reward and Benefit System Management on Staff Productivity in Edo State Ministry of Education

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Abstract

Employees' productivity in Nigerian public sector is known to be relatively low compared with those of their counterparts in other developing and developed countries. The above phenomenon has been linked to poor reward and benefit system management. Most employees experience low level of motivation in their workplaces due to several factors, such as, low morale, job dissatisfaction, and general lack of work incentives. It is in this context that the article examined various reward and benefit system management as means of staff productivity in Edo State Ministry of Education, using a qualitative research methods, that depended on the judgmental sampling technique, and a sample size of 20 respondents, as well as, the application of both primary and secondary method of data collection. In addition, the textual analysis techniques was applied in the analysis of both the primary and secondary data collected for the study. Findings from the study revealed that there is inadequate provision of reward to staff of Edo State Ministry of Education (ESME). Also, the research found that the administration of monetary rewards to staff of Edo State Ministry of Education is not adequate for enhancement of their productivity, amongst others. The article recommended that the government should make provision for enhanced monetary and non-monetary rewards to employees of ESME to ensure staff productivity and achievement of a better service delivery; the administration of rewards and benefit systems in ESME should be implemented in accordance to employees' performance in the workplace to encourage hard working staff, and to also, discourage laziness among employees; among others.

Keywords: Benefit system, fringe benefits, management, reward, staff productivity

1. Introduction

Globally, reward administration has been of utmost significance to organizational growth and development. It is in this perspective that Oh and Lewis (2013, cited in Pillah, 2023) conducted a study on impacts of administration of rewards on performance in the United States of America federal civil service, and found the existence of a strong positive relationship between rewards and performance of civil servants. Employees will increase their performance when they perceive that their contributions to the organizations will attract positive outcome from management (Osazevaru & Ogbuma, 2024). Fringe benefits are rewards granted to employees in addition to payment of salaries (Akpan, 2020). These pension benefits, medical insurance, study leave with pay and other education sponsorship programmes, time off, maternity leave, paid vacation among others (Oaya, Mambula & Anyatonwu, 2019; Ifediniru, 2012).

The popularity of studies on reward and benefit system management is based on the fact that employees are the most valuable organizational assets in organisations (Werner & Desimone, 2020). Reward and benefit system management is one of the surest means of attaining employees higher job productivity in Nigeria (Osazevaru & Ogbuma, 2024). This article examined the impact of reward and benefit system management on staff productivity in Edo State Ministry of Education (ESME).

There has been the agitation for enhanced remuneration of employees of the Nigerian public sector in recent times, which gave rise to the enactment of the minimum wage of N70, 000 by the Federal Government of Nigeria (Osazevaru & Ogbuma, 2024). The minimum wage was subjected to further agitation for more increment due to erosion of its purchasing power by the present high rate of inflation in the country (Osazevaru & Ogbuma, 2024). Public sector, according to Osisioma and Osisioma (2009, cited in Odeh and Unufe, 2019, p. 165) is the “public realm where goal-oriented public policies are implemented for the attainment of common interest.” The absence of motivational incentives in workplaces reverse the gains of organizational productivity (Osazevaru & Ogbuma, 2024; Shin-Rong & Chin-Wen, 2024; Mayson & Barrett, 2016) While majority of the studies on effective reward and benefit system management on staff productivity were carried out in various public services in Nigeria, none of the study was conducted in ESME, Nigeria. This, therefore, constitute the gap which this study is designed to fill.

The main objective of the study is to examine reward and benefit system management on staff productivity in the public service of Nigeria. While the specific objectives are to determine the relationship between monetary rewards and staff productivity in ESME; examine the effects of non-monetary incentives on staff productivity in ESME; and investigate the impacts of fringe benefit on staff productivity in ESME. To facilitate the achievement of its objectives, the study is divided into various sections, such as the introduction, statement of the problem, research questions, objectives of the study, conceptual clarification, literature review, theoretical framework, methodology, discussions of findings, conclusion and recommendations.

1.1. Operational Clarification of Terms

i. Reward Administration

Reward administration refers to the monetary rewards and fringe benefits which are granted to employees by their organizations which, comprises their holistic benefits (Ogbonnaya, Gambo, Abubakar, 2024). Rewards are incentives given to workers for the accomplishment of their assigned tasks, and it is also a means of motivating them for higher performance. The non-monetary rewards can include praise from managers, supervisors and colleagues, prospects for future promotion, perception of self-esteem due to outstanding achievements and recognition (Lawler, 1973, cited in Ogbonnaya et al., 2024).

ii. Staff Productivity

Productivity is centered on effective and efficient discharge of assigned tasks (Nwachukwu, 2006). Staff productivity refers to the comparison between the achievement of the actual work output of an employee and initial target set for achievement (Atuma, 2021). Staff productivity comprises the behaviour exhibited by employees which are necessary to the realization of goals of organizations (Mugaa, Guyo & Odiambo, 2018). It can simply be described as employees’ achievements or accomplishments (Nisar & Danish, 2019).

2. Literature Review

It has been identified that both extrinsic and intrinsic motivational approaches translate to improved staff productivity (Quresh et al., 2019; Ahiabor, 2019; Aktar & Pangil, 2018; Zaraket & Saber, 2017; Kwenin, Muathe & Nzulwa, 2013; Ong & Teh, 2012). For example, A study conducted within cement companies in Pakistan, found that the adoption of both intrinsic and extrinsic motivational techniques translate

to improved staff productivity. Reward and benefit system management determine staff performance and Productivity (Ogbonnaya et al., 2024; Sajuyigbe et al., 2013; Yamoah, 2013). Similarly, reward administration in the workplace translate to generation of innovative ideas by employees (Stajkovic, Bandura, Locke, Lee & Sergent, 2018). The above studies implies that both the monetary and non-monetary rewards virtually have equal motivational strength. The payment of the salaries of public sector managers as and when due is responsible for staff productivity (Bull, 2005, cited in Abiri, Adedapo & Adenagbe, 2024), and bureaucratic performance (Ifaka & Odigie, 2021). An enhanced salary payment can improve employee job satisfaction and reduce workers' turnover, as well as ensuring staff productivity (Ogbonnaya et al., 2024).

The non-monetary incentives have been identified to be more effective in staff motivation than the monetary rewards (Abiri et al., 2024; Okwudili & Ogbu, 2017; Emerole & Edeh, 2017; Robbins, 2013). For instance, Okwudili and Ogbu (2017) conducted a study among selected Government Parastatals in Abia State, Nigeria, and found that higher staff productivity of public servants is achieved through the application of non- monetary incentives as means of motivation in the workplace. These studies have contradicted previous numerous studies that agreed that remuneration translates to improvement in employees' productivity.

In Nigeria, reward and benefit administration has been observed to be responsible for enhanced workers performance in organizations (Ogbonnaya et al., 2024; Oseremen, Agbonna, Oluyode & Yakubu, 2023; Awotunde & Ojo, 2022, cited in Pillah, 2023; Ele, Makama & Auquasama, 2020; Nnubia, 2020; Onuora, Okeke & Ikechukwu, 2019; Okeke, Nwele & Achilike, 2017). For example, Onwuka and Onwuchekwa (2018) stated that the implementation of benefit programmes lead to enhanced commitment of workers and job performance in the workplace. Conversely, it has been observed that inadequate reward administration leads to low staff productivity and employees' turnover (Bornstein, 2019; Oyedele (2016). The above studies imply that the provision of adequate rewards lead to enhanced staff productivity in the Nigerian public service.

2.1. Implications of Fringe Benefits to Staff Productivity

Fringe benefits refers to indirect rewards granted to workers as additional packages to their main salary (Young & Jin, 2018, cited in Osazevbaru & Ogbuma, 2024; Mugaa, Guyo & Odiambo, 2018). Thus, fringe benefits refers to a broad range of benefits other than wages and salaries, which are supplementary in nature, and perhaps not worked for and are often offered to all employees, irrespective of their different performances. Example of fringe benefits include annual "leave allowance, salary advance, educational assistance, and pension benefits" (A1-Nsour, 2012, cited in Osazevbaru & Ogbuma, 2024; Osazevbaru & Ogbuma, 2024, p. 30). Fringe benefits enhance employees' job performance and satisfaction (Atuma, 2021; Iyida, 2015). "Pension is the sum of money paid to an elderly worker by his or her employer or organization which he or she has worked for after disengaging from the work on the ground of merit consideration" (Fashagba & Dunmade, 2019, cited in Odeh & Nwosu, 2024, p. 2). The imperatives of pension benefits for Nigerian public servants were aptly captured in Section 173 (1) of the 1999 amended constitution of Nigeria, and the Pension Reform Act 2014 of Nigeria (Odeh, 2024). Pension benefits translate to staff productivity in organizations (Audu & Gungul, 2014, cited in Abiri et al., 2024; Orakwe, 2021; Akpan, 2020). Similarly, in Nigeria, "upon retirement or the attainment of age 50, an employee is entitled to his or her pension benefits" (Odeh Oladejo, 2024, p. 202).

On a contrary note, a recent study among employees of public universities in Nigeria found that retirement benefits has no positive effect on non-academic staff productivity (Abiri et al., 2024). This findings contradicted previous findings cited in this article. Its contradictory position may be due to the poor public perception of previous pension systems in Nigeria, especially, among Nigerian public sector workers most of whom had terrible experiences in the previous pension plan. Briscoe, Aiwuyo,

and Iwuagwu (2023, p. 101) conducted a study in Edo Central Senatorial District of Edo State, Nigeria, and found “no significant relationship between monetary incentives and teacher performance”.

A similar study conducted among public universities in Ogun State of Nigeria, identified several factors militating against staff job satisfaction. These include increased workload, low salary level and allowances, absence of housing and car loans, as well as, poor organizational culture (Oseremen et al., 2023). A study conducted among civil servants in Delta State, Nigeria, revealed that the motivation, commitment, and job engagement of staff lead to job satisfaction, and the achievement of the above is based on availability of fringe benefits (Osazevaru Ogbuma, 2024). Furthermore, Obiora (2012) conducted a study in the Civil Service of Anambra State, Nigeria, and observed that staff morale and productivity is determined by effective reward and benefit system management. In addition, a comfortable physical work environment translates to an enhanced job performance of employees (Robbins, Coulter & Randel, 2021; Miller, Shenhav & Ludvig, 2019).

3. Theoretical Framework

3.1. Herzberg Two-Factor Theory

Fredrick Herzberg Two-Factor theory is a popular motivational theory that best explains reward and benefit system management in organizations. The theory was propounded in 1959, and argues that organizations’ staff have two categories of human needs, such as the need for the survival of employees, and the need for growth and advancement of employees. Herzberg refers to needs for survival as hygiene factors, and the needs for personal growth as motivators. The hygiene factors do not lead to job satisfaction, but they only prevent job dissatisfaction. Examples of hygiene factors are salaries and wages, job security, company policy and administration, working conditions, interpersonal relationship, and supervision. On the other hand, examples of motivators are achievement, recognition, responsibility, advancement, the work itself, and challenging tasks (Werner & Desimone, 2020; Fadia & Fadia, 2009; Naidu, 1996).

Herzberg noted that the motivator factors create perception of job satisfaction in employees, but job dissatisfaction does not occur when they are absent in organizations. Also, Herzberg two-factor theory implies that organizations must make provision for both hygiene factors to prevent job dissatisfaction, and motivators to provide employees’ motivation. The Herzberg two-factor theory, which is also referred to as motivation-hygiene theory buttressed the argument that non-monetary rewards administered by organizations are as efficacious as monetary rewards in the motivation of employees (Fadia & Fadia, 2009; Naidu, 1996). Reward and benefit system management is an approach adopted by organizations to attract, reduce employees’ turnover, and incentivize them to enhance their productivity, as well as, making them compliant to organizational policies and regulations (Njanja, Maina, Kibet1 & Njagi, 2013). The application of Fredrick Herzberg Two-Factor theory to this paper is based on the fact that effective rewards and benefit system management tend to cause improved productivity among staff of Edo State Ministry of Education and overall achievement of public service performance.

4. Methodology

The research adopted the qualitative research methods, which is based on both primary and secondary method of data collection. The primary data were collected using the in-depth interview techniques, while the secondary data collection was based on consultation of text books, academic journal articles, internet sources, and so on. The adoption of this method is sequel to its easy application and cost implications, unlike the quantitative survey research approach characterized with large data collection and complicated statistical analysis. The textual analysis techniques was further adopted in the analysis of the collected primary and secondary data. The research was conducted among staff of Edo State Ministry of Education (ESME), Benin City, Nigeria. The judgmental sampling technique was applied

in collecting a total sample size of twenty (20) employees in ESME. The chosen employees cut across the various cadres of ESME, such as the clerical, executive, and administrative/professional cadres. The researcher was assisted by three other interviewers who were earlier given a brief instruction on the modalities to be followed in the interview process to facilitate achievement of objectives of the field research.

5. Analysis and Results

5.1. The Impact of Reward and Benefit System Management on Staff Productivity

The above subject was operationalized through the application of in-depth interview techniques, which involves asking the respondents several oral questions that are in line with the research questions formulated for this study.

5.1.1. Monetary rewards and staff productivity in Edo State Ministry of Education

For example, one of the questions the respondents were asked states that: "Is the administration of monetary rewards to staff of ESME adequate for enhancement of their performance? The responses of most interviewees to the above question was in the negative. For instance, one of the interviewee who was asked the above question stated that: "No! It is not adequate as a result of the increase in cost of living and inflation. There is need for other rewards, such as bonuses and excess work allowances." Similarly, when other respondents were asked the question: "Do you think that the application of monetary rewards to employees of ESME can improve staff productivity?" most of them answered in the affirmative. For example, a respondent observed that: "Yes, monetary rewards can go a long way to improve the productivity of staff in (their) respective Ministries. It motivates staff to want to go extra miles to have his/her work done and promptly delivered."

5.1.2. Non-monetary incentives on staff productivity in Edo State Ministry of Education

Similarly, another question asked by the researcher is stated as follows: "Do you agree that non-monetary incentives are better than monetary incentives with respect to improvement of staff productivity?" In line with the above stated question, several respondents agreed that non-monetary incentives are more effective than monetary incentives with respect to improved staff productivity. For example, a respondent noted that:

Whereas, monetary incentives can be motivating, the non-monetary incentives in my own opinion are more likely to improve (to have a better improvement) on staff productivity. Such things like praise, encouragement, and the like go a long way to make the staff feel accepted, welcomed and a part of the decision making process of the organization. It has a way of boosting the confidence, ego, moral and enthusiasm of the worker. All of these are what the monetary incentive may not be able to provide. The inner satisfaction a staff gets from non-monetary incentives will go a long way (to) increase productivity.

A further question was asked by the researcher, such as: "Do you observe the existence of adequate non-monetary rewards in ESME?" most of the responses to the above question were positive. A case in view, is the response of a respondent stated below: "Yes, there are other rewards apart from monetary (reward), such as gift for the best outstanding person in any of the Ministry (that is, the best worker of the year). This is usually awarded." The above views generally portray inadequate motivational incentives for the staff of ESME, as well as mixed view between the application of monetary and non-monetary incentives.

5.1.3. The impacts of fringe benefit on staff productivity in Edo State Ministry of Education

Furthermore, the respondents were asked a question which include: "In addition, to main salary payment, are there any other rewards, such as leave allowance, salary advance, educational assistance,

regular pension entitlements, housing benefits, social security, unemployment benefit, provision of staff accommodation, disability, protection from loss of income, pension benefits, tuition fees reimbursement, sick leave, maternity leave, granted to staff of ESME?” In line with the above questions, most of the respondents stated that only few of the above stated fringe benefits are provided for the staff of ESME, which of course are not enough to enhance staff productivity. For instance, a respondent interviewed stated that: “Among the benefits highlighted above, the only available benefits are sick leave and maternity leave, which are not enough to motivate workers to a higher productivity. However, if they are available, workers’ productivity will be enhanced”.

6. Discussion of Findings

The findings from the study are presented in line with the stated objectives of the research.

Monetary rewards and staff productivity in Edo State Ministry of Education

Findings from the study revealed that the administration of monetary rewards to staff of ESME is not adequate for enhancement of their performance. Therefore, further findings from the research shows that the application of monetary rewards to employees of ESME can improve staff productivity. This findings is in line with the view that an organisation’s capacity to increase entrants of employees, while at the same time reducing their turnover, through granting of monetary rewards and incentives lead to enhanced organizational performance and growth (Mayson & Barrett, 2016).

Non-monetary incentives on staff productivity in Edo State Ministry of Education

Other findings from the research indicate that non-monetary incentives are more effective than monetary incentives with respect to improvement of staff productivity in ESME. This findings is in line with what Frederick Herzberg described in his Two-Factor Theory as motivators, which include: achievement, advancement, recognition, responsibility, the work itself, and so on. The study also found that indirect motivational approach, such as fringe benefits, which include pension benefits and others can translate to staff productivity in ESME if judiciously administered. Despite the above facts, findings from this research revealed inadequate provision of fringe benefits to staff of ESME. In addition, this present research established the fact that the observed absence of fringe benefits in ESME have adverse consequences on staff productivity. Other findings from the research shows the existence of non-monetary rewards in ESME, but the implementation is inadequate, and hence they are unable to achieve staff productivity. Also, findings from the research revealed that the application of monetary rewards to employees of ESME can in addition, to the application of non-monetary rewards improve productivity of staff of ESME. Therefore, the research concludes that both the monetary and non-monetary rewards can improve staff productivity, but they operate at different level of effectiveness, with the non-monetary rewards being adjudged as more effective than the monetary. This position is supported by Frederick Herzberg in his Two-Factor Theory which argues that the non-monetary rewards which he described as motivators are those factors responsible for employees’ motivation in workplaces.

7. Conclusion and Recommendations

7.1. Conclusion

1. It has been observed that employees will increase their performance when they perceive that their contributions to the organizations will attract positive outcome from management. It is in this context that the article examined the impact of reward and benefit system management on staff productivity in ESME, using the qualitative research methods, which is based on both the primary and secondary methods of data collection. Findings from the study showed that the administration of monetary rewards to staff of ESME is not adequate for enhancement of their performance. Other findings reveal inadequate provision of fringe benefits to staff of ESME, amongst others. 2. The study recommended that the administration of rewards and benefit systems in ESME should be implemented in accordance to employees’ performance

in the workplace to encourage hard working staff, and to also, discourage laziness among employees. Also, the government should make provision for enhanced monetary rewards to employees of ESME to ensure staff productivity and achievement of a better service delivery.

7.2. Recommendations

The following policy recommendations were suggested in the paper as measures aimed at facilitating effective reward and benefit management in Edo State Ministry of Education.

1. The government should make provision for enhanced monetary rewards to employees of Edo State ministry of Education to ensure staff productivity and achievement of a better service delivery.
2. The Edo State Government should ensure adequate provision of fringe benefits to staff of Edo State ministry of Education to enhance their job performances and overall achievement of the objectives of the ministry.
3. The government of Edo State should ensure the prevalence of transparency and accountability in administration of reward incentives to employees of Edo State ministry of Education to ensure effective and efficient implementation of the ministry policy and programmes.
4. The administration of rewards and benefit systems in Edo State ministry of Education should be implemented in accordance to employees' performance in the workplace to encourage hard working staff, and to also, discourage laziness among employees.

References

- Abiri, O. C., Adedapo, A. A., & Adenagbe, O. A. (2024). Remuneration and retirement benefit as correlates of non-academic staff productivity in Nigerian universities. *British Journal of Education*, *12*(2), 32–44. <https://doi.org/10.37745/bje.2013/vol12n23244>
- Ahiabor, G. (2019). The impact of incentives on productivity of firms in Ghana: A case study of Ghana Airport Company Limited. *Problems of Management in the 21st Century*, *8*, 14–15. <https://doi.org/10.33225/pmc/13.08.06b>
- Akpan, U. I. (2020). The impact of fringe benefits on employees' performance and development in Nigerian banking sector. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts*, *8*(6), 1296–1313.
- Aktar, A., & Pangil, F. (2018). Mediating role of organizational commitment in the relationship between human resource management practices and employee engagement: Does black box stage exist? *International Journal of Sociology and Social Policy*, *38*(7-8), 606–636. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSSP-08-2017-0097>
- Atuma, O. (2021). Fringe benefits and employees' performance in the bank of industry limited, Lagos. *Gusau International Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, *4*(3), 108–125.
- Bornstein, S. (2019). The statutory public interest in closing the pay gap. *Alabama Civil Rights and Civil Liberties Law Review*, *10*(1). <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3423121>
- Briscoe, P., Aiwuyo, O. M., & Iwuagwu, O. B. (2023). The (non) influence of monetary incentives on teacher job performance in Edo Central Senatorial District, Nigeria. *World Journal of Educational Research*, *10*(2), 101–118. <http://dx.doi.org/10.22158/wjer.v10n2p101>

- Ele, A. A., Makama, L. L., & Auquasama, A. V. (2020). Salaries and wages management: An instrumental tool for effective development of civil servants' performance in Cross River State, Nigeria. *American International Journal of Supply Chain Management*, 1(1), 16–29.
- Emerole, O. B., & Edeh, F. O. (2017). The effect of compensation on employee performance in Nigeria Civil Service: A study of Rivers State Board of Internal Revenue Service. *Journal of Strategic Human Resource Management*, 6(2), 9–16. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3480547>
- Fadia, B. L., & Fadia, K. (2009). *Public administration*. Agra: Sahitya Bhawan Publications.
- Hong, J. C., Yang, S. D., Wang, L. J., Chiou, E. F., Sun, F. Y., & Huang, T. L. (2015). Impact of employee benefits on work motivation and productivity. *The International Journal of Career Management*, 7(6), 10–14.
- Ifaka, J. O., & Odigie, C. (2021). Political interference and bureaucratic performance in Nigeria: A human resource trajectory of the muffling of bureaucratic capacity. *Global Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 9(7), 63–75.
- Ifediniro, K. U. (2012). A survey of the effects of benefits on employees performance in the hospitality industry: A case study of Sofitel De Moor house, Ikeja Lagos. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 5(5), 1–9.
- Iyida, M. N. (2015). The effect of increase in wage and fringe benefits on the productivity of workers in Nigeria: A case study of Federal Ministry of Transportation, Enugu, Nigeria. *Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Sciences*, 3(1), 13–18.
- Kwenin, D. O., Muathe, S., & Nzulwa, R. (2013). The influence of employee rewards, human resource policies and job satisfaction on the retention of employees in Vodafone Ghana Limited. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 5(12), 13–20.
- Mayson, S., & Barrett, R. (2016). Getting and keeping good staff: An analysis of human resource management “problems” in small firms. *Report to CPA Australia*, 23(4), 56–78.
- Miller, K. J., Shenhav, A., & Ludvig, E. A. (2019). Habits without values. *Psychological Review*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/rev0000120>
- Mugaa, L., Guyo, W., & Odiambo, S. (2018). Influence of fringe benefits on employee performance in large commercial banks in Nairobi City County in Kenya. *Journal of Strategic Management*, 2(2), 31–49.
- Naidu, S. P. (1996). *Public Administration: Concepts and theories*. New Age International (P) Limited Publishers.
- Nisar, S., & Danish, A. (2019). A survey on the role of fringe benefit in employee satisfaction. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 9(1), 232–252.
- Njanja, W. L., Maina, R. N., Kibet, L. K., & Njagi, K. (2013). Effect of reward on employee performance: A case of Kenya Power and Lighting Company Ltd., Nakuru, Kenya. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 8(21), 41–49. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/ijbm.v8n21p41>

- Nnubia, A. L. (2020). Monetary incentives and employee performance of manufacturing firms in Anambra State. *International Journal of Innovative Finance and Economics Research*, 8, 10–22.
- Nwachukwu, C. C. (2006). *Management: Theory and practice* (2nd ed.). Africana Fep. Publishers.
- Oaya, Z. C., Mambula, C. J., & Anyatonwu, P. (2019). Impact of fringe benefits on employee performance: A study of Nasco Group, Jos Plateau State. *Journal of Management*, 1(1), 1–21.
- Obiora, C. M. (2012). Wage administration and productivity in Anambra State civil service, Nigeria. *African Research Review*, 6(4), 121–134.
- Odeh, L. O. (2024). Contending issues in trade unionism and contributory pension reform in Nigeria: The experience of Delta State public service. *International Review of Business and Applied Sciences*, 5(1), 86–112.
- Odeh, L. O., & Nwosu, U. V. (2024). Implementation, prospects and challenges of the contributory pension policy in Nigeria: A theoretical review. *Covenant Journal of Business & Social Sciences (CJBSS)*, 15(1), 1–20.
- Odeh, L. O., & Oladejo, J. O. (2024). Retirees' level of awareness of contributory pension policy in Delta State of Nigeria: Issues and prospects. *Nigerian Journal of Management Sciences*, 25(2), 201–210.
- Odeh, L. O., & Unufe, J. (2019). Due process and accountability mechanisms in the Nigerian public service. *Lapai Journal of International Politics*, 5(4 & 5), 162–174.
- Ogbonnaya, S. C., Gambo, N., & Abubakar, H. S. (2024). Compensation administration and employee's performance among private universities in North Central Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Management Review*, 12(5), 39–70. <https://doi.org/10.37745/ijbmr.2013/vol12n53970>
- Okeke, A. C., Nwele, O. C., & Achilike, H. U. (2017). Effective wages and salary administration and productivity in civil service in Nigeria: A case of Anambra state civil service. *Asian Journal of Applied Science and Technology (AJAST)*, 1(9), 421–438.
- Okwudili, B., & Ogbu, E. (2017). The effect of compensation on employee performance in Nigeria. *Journal of Strategic Human Resource Management*, 6(2).
- Ong, S., & Teh, H. (2012). Reward system and performance within Malaysian manufacturing companies. Faculty of Economics and Management, University Putra Malaysia, Malaysia.
- Onuora, A. N., Okeke, M. N., & Ikechukwu, I. A. (2019). Compensation management and employee performance in Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 9(2), 384–394. <https://doi.org/10.6007/IJARBSS/v9-v2/5552>
- Onwuka, E. M., & Onwuchekwa, F. (2018). Compensation management and organizational performance: A study of selected pharmaceutical companies in Awka, Anambra State. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)*, 20(9), 36–47. <https://doi.org/10.9790/487X-2009033647>
- Orakwe, C. A. (2021). Compensation packages and civil servants' performance in state ministries in Anambra State. *International Journal of Innovative Development and Policy Studies*, 9(1), 1112–1261.

- Osazevbaru, H. O., & Ogbuma, S. M. (2024). Fringe benefits and employee performance in the Nigerian civil service: A study of selected Local Government Councils in Delta State, Nigeria. *Business Management Gph - International Journal*, 7(8), 28–38. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13729471>
- Oseremen, N. O., Agbonna, R. O., Oluyode, Q. N., & Yakubu, A. O. (2023). Assessment of the relationship between fringe benefits and staff job satisfaction in public universities in Ogun State. *Sapientia Global Journal of Arts, Humanities and Development Studies*, 6(1), 57–69.
- Oyedele, O. J. (2016). Wage or salary administration practice and its implications for national development: The Nigerian experience. *Journal of Public Administration, Finance and Law*, 9(2), 27–34.
- Pillah, T. P. (2023). Federal civil service remuneration and salary in Nigeria: An overview of structural change. *International Journal of Public Administration and Management Research (IJPAMR)*, 8(6), 62–72.
- Qureshi, M. A., Qureshi, J. A., Thebo, J. A., Shaikh, G. M., Broh, N. A., & Qaise, S. (2019). The nexus of employee's commitment, job satisfaction, and job performance: An analysis of FMCG industries of Pakistan. *Cogent Business & Management*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2019.1654189>
- Robbins, S. P., Coulter, M., & Randel, A. (2021). *Management*. United Kingdom: Pearson Education Ltd.
- Robbins, P. S. (2013). *Organizational behaviour* (12th ed.). New Delhi: Pearson Prentice Hall of India.
- Sajuyigbe, A. S., Olaoye, B. O., & Adeyemi, M. A. (2013). Impact of reward on employees' performance in a selected manufacturing companies in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Arts and Commerce*, 2(2), 27–32.
- Shin-Rong, S., & Chin-Wen, H. F. (2024). Performance of financial hedging and earnings management under diverse corporate information quality. *International Review of Economics & Finance*, 782–810. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iref.2024.01.058>
- Stajkovic, A. D., Bandura, A., Locke, E. A., Lee, D., & Sergent, K. (2018). Test of three conceptual models of influence of the big five personality traits and self-efficacy on academic performance: A meta analytic path-analysis. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 120, 238–245.
- Werner, J. M., & DeSimone, R. L. (2023). *Human resource development*. United States of America: South Western Cengage Learning.
- Werner, J. M., & DeSimone, R. L. (2020). *Human Resource Development* (8th ed.). Cengage Learning.
- Yamoah, E. E. (2013). Relationship between compensation and employee productivity. *Singaporean Journal of Business Economics and Management Studies*, 2(1), 110–114.
- Zaraket, W. S., & Saber, F. (2017). The impact of financial reward on job satisfaction and performance: Implications for blue-collar employees. *China-USA Business Review*, 16(8), 369–378.